

D7.8 – HORUS website

Project Information

Project Full Title	Casting light on HOst-cytomegaloviRUs interaction in Solid organ Transplantation
Project Acronym	HORUS
Call	HORIZON-HLTH-2021-DISEASE-04
Start date of the project	1 November 2022
Duration	60 Months
Project Coordinator	Hannah Kaminski, Associate Professor, MD PhD
Project Website	https://www.horus-project.eu/

Deliverable Information

Deliverable n°	7.8
Deliverable title	HORUS website
WP n°	7
Lead Beneficiary	ESOT
Type	DEC
Due Date	2023-01-31
Submission Date	2023-04-06

Dissemination Level

PU	Public	X
SEN	Sensitive	

Document Log

Version	Date	Author	Description of Change
V1	2023-04-06	Chiara Parisotto (ESOT), Stéphanie Grégoire (UBx)	Final

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1 Executive Summary

Deliverable D7.8 is a report on the HORUS Project website, which can be considered one of the most relevant dissemination tools to be used by the project consortium to reach a wide public and communicate project progress and results. Therefore, the main content of this document is focused on the description of the project website in terms of design, structure, and content.

2 Introduction

The development of the website of the HORUS project is one of the activities related to WP7 dealing with the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of the results of the project. ESOT has been in charge of the development of the website. The website can be found in the following URL: <https://www.horus-project.eu/>

3 Main objectives

Project websites are one of the main communication tools of projects funded under the European Commission, Horizon Europe. To ensure maximum visibility to the HORUS objectives and results, we have set up a squarespace project website registered in the “eu” domain and with intuitive URLs to increase hit rates: <https://www.horus-project.eu/>

The design of the website builds upon the following criteria:

- I. **Visual communication:** use of colours and photos, web pages are easy to browse, information is kept short, and links are included to websites, publications, and so on.
- II. **Verbal communication:** the website uses simple phrasing, no jargon is used to attract the widest possible audience, and e-devices are user-friendly.
- III. **Visibility:** maximum use of free or affordable methods to increase page ranking on search engines, Webmaster Tools provided by search engines to check indexing status, good cross-linking between the different pages of the site, adding keywords to the web page metadata; use of frequently used keyword search phrases both in the metadata and in the content’s pages.
- IV. **Regular update of contents:** the website is maintained by ESOT, and the updating will be regularly done by the Webmaster upon inputs of the Project Dissemination Manager and partners. The use of social media (Social networks such as Twitter and LinkedIn) has been considered.
- V. **Monitoring and feedback tools:** the website is linked to Google Analytics and Google Search Console to measure the number of visits and analyse the traffic both from a quantitative and quality point of view.

4 Description of the public website

The public section of HORUS website provides the following:

- a brief overview of the project and further details about its objectives, structure and expected impacts;
- the composition of the project consortium, the links to the partners’ websites and the contact of the project coordinator;
- information about HORUS news & events

- project library [open access publications and public deliverables]
- the possibility to sign up to the HORUS newsletter
- get in touch with the HORUS consortium

The public website has several sections and sub-sections devoted to presenting the project to external visitors, all accessible from the home page and described in detail in the following paragraphs.

In each section, at the bottom of the pages, you can find:

- the acknowledgement of the EU co-funding, also by the inclusion of the relevant logo claiming that this project received funding from the European Union's
- the social media bar with HORUS social profiles: [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#);
- some HORUS project details

4.1 Home page

The home page of the website introduces the HORUS project, showing the link to the most relevant pages of the website.

The logo and the project's full name can be seen on the top of the home page. The acknowledgement of the EU funds and the participation of the project to Horizon Europe is prominently shown in the footer of the website and visible throughout the pages.

At the bottom of the home page, the “Sign up to the HORUS Newsletter” button has been indicated.

HORUS: Casting light on **HO**st-cytomegalovi**RU**s interaction in **Solid** organ transplantation

The HORUS project unites solid organ transplantation (SOT) experts, computational data scientists, virologists and immunologists in a fully operating European network consisting of 24 partners.

SOT is the optimal treatment for end-stage organ failure. However, the immunosuppressive drugs used to prevent graft rejection increase the risk of opportunistic infections. Among these infections, cytomegalovirus (CMV) leads to the most frequent morbidity, and can lead to mortality.

The ambitious but realistic goal of HORUS is to improve our understanding of CMV/host interactions in the context of immunosuppression, with a particular focus on:

1. The characterisation of signatures associated with the control of CMV replication after transplantation
2. The characterisation of signatures associated with evolution toward a difficult-to-treat CMV disease and poor outcome during CMV replication
3. The discovery of new specific immunomodulatory molecules promoting CMV control while maintaining the prevention of acute rejection

[SIGN UP TO THE HORUS NEWSLETTER](#)

[Privacy Policy](#)

HORUS project has received funding from HORIZON Europe under the grant agreement No. 101057651

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4.2 Project

The label “Project” on the main menu introduces a page dedicated to the project aims, main objectives and expected results.

The screenshot shows the 'Project' page of the HORUS website. At the top, there is a navigation menu with the following items: HOME, PROJECT (highlighted), CONSORTIUM, EVENTS, NEWS, PROJECT LIBRARY, and CONTACT. Below the navigation is a large teal banner with the text 'PROJECT' and 'Our values are equity, solidarity, sustainability and innovation.' The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column has a section titled 'Overview' with three paragraphs of text. The right column contains two images: the top one shows a person in a white lab coat, and the bottom one shows a close-up of a person's face. At the bottom of the page, there is a grey footer area containing social media icons for Twitter and LinkedIn, a green button that says 'SIGN UP TO THE HORUS NEWSLETTER', a link to 'Privacy Policy', a 'Funded by the European Union' logo, and a disclaimer.

HORUS HOME PROJECT CONSORTIUM EVENTS NEWS PROJECT LIBRARY CONTACT

PROJECT

Our values are equity, solidarity, sustainability and innovation.

Overview

HORUS involves the first longitudinal cohort of European SOT recipients. In a sub-“HORUS-exploratory cohort”, we will perform a thorough investigation of viral, clinical and immunological characteristics.

Combining those parameters will provide a signature early after transplantation to predict the risk of developing CMV infection and a signature at Day 0 of infection to predict the risk of CMV disease severity.

This signature will then be validated retrospectively by the whole cohort and prospectively in a ‘proof-of-concept’ study. Moreover, HORUS will include functional in vitro and mouse models to investigate the mechanisms of lymphocyte response to CMV and provide innovative methods to increase CMV-specific immunity.

Altogether, HORUS will enhance personalised clinical prevention and the treatment of CMV disease, ultimately improving patient outcomes.

[SIGN UP TO THE HORUS NEWSLETTER](#)

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4.3 Consortium

In this section, the list of HORUS’s partners is displayed. For each partner, the logo is shown, and a description of the partner and its role in the project is described.

univ **université** **BORDEAUX**

CHU BDX **CENTRE HOSPITALIER UNIVERSITAIRE BORDEAUX**

HCL

Lyon 1

UKE

INSERM

PAREAN **Biotechnologies** **Deep Immune Phenotyping**

FOCH

CNRS

iCan **Recherche pour l'Innovation en Oculoneurologie et Ophtalmologie**

Université de Limoges

CHU **Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Limoges**

IDI BELL

Vall d'Hebron **Barcelona University Hospital**

CHUV

Unil **UNIL | Université de Lausanne**

Université De Bordeaux (UJ3)

Immunocogent is focusing on questions related to the causes of immune competence deterioration during the course of adult life. Besides chronological age, weakening of the immune system can result from clinical situations associated to an accelerated immune ageing such as infections, transplantation and cancer. Improving our comprehension of immune vulnerability and ageing mechanisms will impact our appreciation of immune

Address
96 rue Leo Segret Campus Caméra
BartB, Bordeaux, 33000, France

Contacts
Hervé Lantard
Julie Dubouché-Monville

Website
<https://immunocogent.chu.fr>

Representatives
Julie Dubouché-Monville
Victor Anjos
Muriel Capone
Amandine Pousset
Stephane Ambroise
Vincent David
Lucas Pouchard
Richard Chouksey
Thierry Vignani
Valérie Comte

4.4 Events

This section is dedicated to relevant events during the lifespan of the HORUS project. This page works as a calendar, and it displays upcoming and past events.

The screenshot shows the 'EVENTS' section of the HORUS website. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for HOME, PROJECT, CONSORTIUM, **EVENTS**, NEWS, PROJECT LIBRARY, and CONTACT. Below the navigation is a large teal banner with the text 'EVENTS' and 'Stay tuned for the latest HORUS events'. Underneath the banner is the 'Upcoming Events' section, which features a calendar icon for 'SEP 17' and a photo of a person in a white lab coat. The text below the photo describes the 'ESOT Congress 2023' as a major event in transplantation, offering networking opportunities. Below this is the 'Past Events' section, which is currently empty. At the bottom of the page, there are social media icons for Twitter and LinkedIn, and a green button that says 'SIGN UP TO THE HORUS NEWSLETTER'.

4.5 News

This section will include the relevant news about the HORUS project and its partners.

News Demo One

23 Feb 2023 - News

This is the excerpt text which gives a brief overview of the article content. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. In consectetur risib vel justo sagittis, dapibus tempor tortor gravida. Donec luctus id neque vel lacinia.

[Read More →](#)

News Demo Two

23 Feb 2023 - Events

This is the excerpt text which gives a brief overview of the article content. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. In consectetur risib vel justo sagittis, dapibus tempor tortor gravida. Donec luctus id neque vel lacinia.

[Read More →](#)

4.6 Project Library

This section will include the scientific publications with the links to the publications as well as all the public deliverables produced over the course of the HORUS project.

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Duis eros urna, fringilla ac euismod vel, accumsan quis mauris. Nullam sed ante ex. Nunc pulvinar metus sed leo posuere, quis commodo velit porttitor. Aenean maximus sem sed rhoncus vestibulum. Cras eleifend, tellus in congue consectetur, ante ligula tincidunt neque, sed lobortis felis sem eu lacus. Praesent mattis neque nisi, eu pretium nulla cursus ac. Quisque dapibus, ligula id faucibus auctor, lectus felis placerat felis, eu dignissim libero tellus a nulla. Nunc quis gravida enim. Phasellus condimentum vitae odio vitae congue. Praesent tristique felis massa, volutpat dictum purus fermentum eget. Aliquam et risus at augue elementum efficitur vitae eu augue. Vivamus eget ipsum in nunc auctor mollis eu ac nunc. Pellentesque ornare cursus leo, eu feugiat augue varius nec. In libero diam, laoreet ac sapien sed, pretium sollicitudin nunc.

4.7 Contact

This section enables people to get in touch easily with the Project Coordinator.

The screenshot shows the contact page of the HORUS website. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for HOME, PROJECT, CONSORTIUM, EVENTS, NEWS, PROJECT LIBRARY, and CONTACT. Below the menu is a green header with the text "CONTACT US". The main content area contains a contact form with the following fields: "Name *" (split into "First Name" and "Last Name"), "Email *", and "Message *". There is a "SUBMIT" button below the message field. To the left of the form, there is a link to "contact@horus-project.eu" and the address: "Address: ESOT Office, Westerdoksdijk 423 - 1013 BX Amsterdam, The Netherlands". Below the address are social media icons for Twitter and LinkedIn. At the bottom of the page, there is a "SIGN UP TO THE HORUS NEWSLETTER" button, a "Privacy Policy" link, and a "Funded by the European Union" logo. A disclaimer at the very bottom states: "HORUS project has received funding from HORIZON Europe under the grant agreement No. 101057651. Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

5 Conclusion

The HORUS project website will be periodically updated by ESOT with the contribution of all the partners of the project. The updates on the website will be related to new conferences, events in which the project will participate, news and/or publications related to HORUS, images and updates from project meetings; public deliverables will be uploaded in the “Project Library” subpage. Finally, a section dedicated to the results of the project will be created: data and images of the materials and technologies developed in the project will be published inside it.